

D2.2

Analytical protocol to assess the build-up forms and public space on street networks

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1. Introduction

This document presents the conceptual and methodological foundations of a protocol designed to assess built-up forms and public space along street networks in the context of the EMC2 project. It corresponds to Part 1 of Deliverable D2.2 and focuses on the analytical framework, the theoretical background, and the logic of the indicators. All implementation

details, including code examples and formal pseudocode, are reserved for Part 2 of the deliverable.

The protocol concentrates on the relationship between street-based morphology and the capacity of streets to function as the structural backbone of urban life, particularly in metropolitan peripheries and suburban areas. It does so by focusing on the built environment as experienced from the street, using the `momepy.streetscape` framework (Araldi et al. 2025) to derive a set of morphometric descriptors, and then emphasising three core indicators:

- **Continuity**, describing the presence and persistence of façades along the street;
- **Alignment**, describing the regularity of façade positions and setbacks;
- **HW Ratio**, describing the relationship between building heights and visible street width, and thus the degree of three-dimensional enclosure.

These indicators are conceived as **skeletal descriptors** of the urban form that frames the street. They do not capture all aspects of street quality – such as entrances, windows, materials or vegetation – but they describe fundamental structural conditions that constrain what kinds of street life and public-space usage can occur. These structural conditions can be derived from a vector-based 2.5D description of buildings, easily available for cities across the world (for example through OSM data). In the wider EMC2 framework and its WP2, they are intended to complement configurational measures of centrality, functional data on activities and services, and socio-demographic indicators to identify street potential to act as main streets within metropolitan areas.

Part 1 of D2.2 is organised as follows. Section 2 offers a theoretical positioning of the protocol, explaining how it relates to EMC2 principles, to broader debates on main streets and public space, and to the distinction between skeletal and “skin” attributes of streetscapes. Section 3 presents the methodological protocol, from data requirements to the construction of streetscape morphometrics using `momepy.streetscape`. Section 4 introduces the three key indicators – Continuity, Alignment and HW Ratio – and describes how they are derived from the underlying morphometrics, providing explicit formulae. Section 5 discusses how these indicators can be combined into a composite interpretation of main-street suitability, including the rationale for using sigmoidal transformations and for calibrating them with points of interest. Section 6 addresses limitations and outlines directions for future development. Section 7 concludes by summarising the role of this protocol within the broader EMC2 project.

Throughout, the objective is to offer a clear, rigorous and transferable protocol that can be applied across different metropolitan case studies, while remaining transparent about its assumptions and open to refinement in subsequent work packages.

2. Theoretical positioning

2.1 EMC2, main streets and the meshed compact city

The EMC2 project proposes the concept of the **evolutive meshed compact city** as a way to reconcile the 15-minute city paradigm with the physical and social realities of European peripheries and suburbs. Instead of assuming a homogeneous city where every point is equally central, EMC2 emphasises the importance of a **foreground mesh** of main streets. These main streets form a network of linear centres that concentrate activities, services and public life within a spatially coherent structure. They are embedded in a wider fabric of residential neighbourhoods, green spaces and local amenities, and connected by multimodal transport options.

Within this perspective, main streets are expected to carry significant flows, but also to function as public spaces that are hospitable for pedestrians, offer opportunities for encounter and interaction, and support a mix of uses and activities. The EMC2 principles (Fusco et al. 2024) explicitly state that main streets should operate as dense and diverse local centres for surrounding areas and that they should exhibit higher built-up density and activity concentration than the areas they serve, while also providing pedestrian-friendly environments with continuous built frontages, limited or well-managed setbacks and a positive degree of spatial enclosure, as already pointed out by a vast body of literature (Alexander et al. 1977, Appleyard 1981, Gehl 2011).

In short, main streets within EMC2 are not merely links in a graph: they are **morpho-functional entities** where network structure, built-up form and public-space qualities converge. The protocol developed in this deliverable aims to operationalise part of this convergence at a metropolitan scale by focusing on the structural properties of **built-up form and public space visual delimitation along the street network**.

2.2 Skeletal streetscape and the “skin” of the street

A key conceptual element of the protocol is the distinction between the **skeletal streetscape** and the **“skin” of the street** (Harvey and Aultman-Hall 2016). The skeletal dimension refers to the arrangement of solid built mass relative to the street: the presence or absence of buildings, their position and spacing, their typical height and the resulting shape of the street corridor. The “skin” comprises more detailed features, such as windows, doors, balconies, materials, colours, shopfronts, vegetation and street furniture.

Both levels matter for public-space quality. The skin strongly influences perceptions of safety, attractiveness and comfort, and it expresses the fine-grained public-private interface. However, the skeletal level constrains what is possible at the skin level. There must be a façade in the first place for windows and doors to exist; there must be a reasonably continuous and well-positioned building line for a coherent street edge to form; and there must be an adequate degree of enclosure before subtle differences in façade treatment can be meaningfully experienced.

The protocol presented here is explicitly designed to work at this **skeletal level**. This choice is motivated by both conceptual and practical considerations. Conceptually, skeletal form is associated with long-term structural properties of urban fabric: building massing and alignment change slowly and often reflect underlying parcel structures and planning decisions. The skin can change more quickly through renovation, façade refurbishment or changes of use. Practically, skeletal features can be reconstructed with reasonable accuracy from datasets that are widely available across European cities, namely street networks and building footprints with height information. This motivates skeletal analysis to be carried out at the metropolitan scale (WP2). In contrast, comprehensive data on entrances, windows and façade treatments are rare, local and heterogeneous. Fine-grained analysis of building types, façades, street vegetation or urban furniture will therefore be carried out only for test areas in the project WP5.

This focus does not imply that the skin is unimportant, but it frames the current work as a **foundation** on which more detailed analyses can later be built.

2.3 Morphological preconditions and constitutedness

The protocol also relates to ideas of **constitutedness** from space syntax theory, where the degree of adjacency and permeability between building interiors and public space is measured through entrances and windows opening directly onto the street. Streets that are “well constituted” in this sense tend to attract and sustain more street life, as they provide frequent transitions between private and public realms and a high density of “contacts” at the edge of the space.

Since the exact locations of entrances and windows are not systematically available in the datasets used at the metropolitan scale, the protocol does not attempt to measure constitutedness directly. Instead, it aims to capture **morphological preconditions** that are likely to support high constitutedness where other conditions (functional mix, socio-economic context, etc.) are favourable.

These preconditions include the existence of a **continuous built front** along the street, a reasonable degree of **Alignment** between façades, and a **HW Ratio** that yields an intelligible and comfortable sense of enclosure. If very little built front exists, or if façades are randomly scattered in depth, or if the street is extremely over-wide relative to building height, then even an abundance of entrances may not produce the qualities typically associated with main streets in the EMC2 model. Conversely, a street with a strong continuous edge and appropriate enclosure is structurally capable of supporting many entrances and windows in a way that resonates with the notion of constitutedness.

In this sense, the indicators developed here do not replace direct interface measures but rather provide a **base layer** that can be complemented with entrance data when available.

2.4 Three skeletal indicators from EMC2 principles

Translating EMC2 principles into measurable descriptors leads naturally to three questions. First, to what extent is the street lined by buildings along its length? This leads to the indicator called **Continuity**. Second, to what extent do these buildings form a consistent line rather than being irregularly set back or pushed forward? This motivates the indicator called **Alignment**. Third, how strongly is the cross-section of the street enclosed by the relative height of buildings and the width of the space between them? This motivates the indicator called **HW Ratio**.

A street that scores highly on Continuity has façades present for most of its length, making it a plausible support for a dense array of entrances, windows and activities. A street that scores highly on Alignment exhibits a legible edge, which helps define public space and supports orientation and visual coherence. A street with a favourable HW Ratio offers a three-dimensional environment that is neither excessively flat and exposed nor oppressively canyon-like.

These three indicators are not exhaustive, but they capture core aspects of the skeletal streetscape that are particularly relevant to EMC2's conception of main streets. They are also amenable to formalisation in relatively simple mathematical terms, which facilitates their application and interpretation across different case studies.

2.5 A via negativa perspective

The protocol adopts a **via negativa** perspective in the sense that it focuses on identifying and penalising morphological conditions that are clearly incompatible with EMC2's expectations for main streets, rather than prescribing a unique ideal morphology. Extremely low Continuity values signal environments dominated by gaps, open land or very distant buildings. Extremely low HW Ratio values indicate over-wide and under-built corridors that lack strong enclosure. Very low Alignment values reveal strongly irregular façade lines.

By defining the indicators and their transformations in such a way that these extreme conditions receive low scores, the protocol delineates a **broad region of morphological acceptability** where a variety of forms can be considered structurally supportive of main-street functions. This avoids a normative imposition of a specific architectural style or typology while still providing a rigorous basis for analysis and comparison.

3. Methodological protocol: from data to streetscape morphometrics

3.1 Data and pre-processing

The practical application of the protocol begins with two main types of geospatial data: a street centreline network and a layer of building footprints. The street network is pre-processed to form a topologically consistent graph where each edge corresponds to an intersection-to-intersection street segment. Each segment is assigned a unique identifier,

denoted s , which serves as the key for joining morphological and activity attributes.

The building footprint layer consists of polygon geometries representing built structures and, where possible, includes an attribute representing building height or number of floors. If only floor counts are available, a typical floor height may be used to estimate absolute building heights. Both the street network and the building footprints are projected into a common coordinate reference system with metric units to ensure consistency of distance-based measurements.

Subsequently, activity data from points of interest (Pols), such as Foursquare venues representing shops, services, restaurants and other amenities, are prepared. These Pols are associated with street segments, for example by counting all Pols that fall within a fixed buffer distance of each segment or by using nearest-street assignment. This results in activity variables for each street s , such as the number of Pols per segment and the density of Pols per unit length. Activity data will be more specifically used in D2.5 of WP2. Here, as explained later, they will be used to calibrate suitability scores of morphometric values.

Before moving to the streetscape analysis, the datasets are cleaned to remove obvious errors, such as duplicated geometries, corrupted features, or buildings completely outside the intended area of study. Street segments corresponding to motorways or non-urban infrastructure may be excluded when they are not relevant for the analysis of built-up public space.

3.2 Data sources, inputs and outputs

This work relies on heterogeneous geospatial datasets describing street networks, building footprints, building heights (where available), and activity locations. All datasets were harmonised into a common spatial reference system and processed into standardised geopackage formats to ensure consistency across the five metropolitan case studies analysed in the EMC2 project.

Street and building input datasets

Street centreline networks are retrieved from OpenStreetMap (OSM) and were pre-processed and filtered in previous phases of the EMC2 project, as documented in Deliverable D1. For the French Riviera and the Lille–Roubaix–Tourcoing metropolitan area, an additional semi-automatic network correction procedure was implemented to improve topological consistency and geometric accuracy. This was done through the *neatnet* python library (Fleischmann et al. 2026) and subsequent manual checks and editings.

Building footprint datasets were obtained from authoritative or widely used open data sources, depending on local availability. Where available, these datasets also provide reliable building height attributes, enabling the computation of all three streetscape morphometrics used in this work (Continuity, Alignment, and HW Ratio).

- i) Lille–Roubaix–Tourcoing and Nice / French Riviera (France): Building data were sourced from IGN BD TOPO®.

- ii) Vienna (Austria): Street and building datasets were obtained from the Austrian open data portal <https://www.data.gv.at/home?locale=de>.
- iii) Versilia (Italy): Building footprints were derived from the Carta Tecnica Regionale (CTR) provided by the regional authorities.
- iv) Gothenburg: Building datasets were obtained from the Chalmers University of Technology urban morphology datasets, which provide high-quality geometric descriptions of the built environment but do not systematically include building height attributes compatible with cross-city comparison.

All harmonised street and building layers are stored in the project input geopackage: *data/input/emc2_streets_buildings.gpkg*

This geopackage contains one street layer and one building layer per city, used as the common input for the streetscape computation pipeline.

Points of Interest (POIs)

Activity data used for calibration were derived from Foursquare Points of Interest. Due to licensing constraints, the raw POI dataset cannot be redistributed. For this reason:

- i) The analytical pipeline does not depend on a specific POI provider. Any comparable POI dataset (e.g. OpenStreetMap amenities, commercial registries, or local business datasets) can be substituted without modifying the methodological logic.
- ii) Raw POI geometries are not included in the shared project archives.
- iii) The pipeline outputs aggregated POI indicators at the street-segment level only, ensuring that no proprietary data are redistributed.

The street-level POI indicators used for calibration (POI counts and POI densities per street segment) are provided in the following output file: *data/output/streets_poi_aggregated.gpkg*.

These attributes are explicitly formatted to serve as inputs for the sigmoid calibration procedures described in Section 5.

Output datasets and derived products

The final outcome of the streetscape analysis is a geopackage containing five layers, one per metropolitan area, stored in: *data/output/emc2_streetscape_results.gpkg*

Each city-specific layer includes:

- i) The full set of streetscape morphometric descriptors computed using *momepy.streetscape* (including more descriptors than those strictly required for this work);
- ii) Aggregated POI indicators at the street-segment level (counts and densities);
- iii) Parameters of the sigmoid fittings obtained under three alternative calibration strategies: calibration using the full street dataset; calibration excluding street segments shorter than 10 metres; calibration excluding short streets and street segments with zero POIs.

- iv) For each calibration strategy: the fitted sigmoid functions for each individual morphometric indicator (Continuity, Alignment, HW Ratio when available); the combined sigmoid representing the overall probabilistic enclosure score (attribute name: enclosed).

The numerical parameters and graphical representations of all fitted sigmoid functions are additionally stored in the following folder *results/sigmoid_plots_prob/*. This folder documents the probabilistic thresholds underlying both the individual indicator sigmoids and the combined enclosed score.

3.3 Streetscape representation with Sight Points and sightlines

The `momepy.streetscape` framework constructs a streetscape representation by placing Sight Points along street segments and emitting sightlines from these points to intersect surrounding buildings. In the present protocol, attention is focused on left and right perpendicular sightlines, as these directly describe cross-sectional relationships between the street and the adjacent built form.

For each street segment s , Sight Points are placed at regular intervals along the centreline. Let Δ denote the chosen spacing between Sight Points. If the length of segment s is L_s , and a short offset is maintained at each end near intersections, then the approximate number of Sight Points is given by:

$$N_s \approx \lfloor (L_s - 2 \cdot \text{offset}) / \Delta \rfloor$$

From each Sight Point, two perpendicular sightlines are generated: one to the left and one to the right, according to the local direction of the street. Each sightline extends from the sampling point outwards up to a maximum distance D_{\max} , chosen large enough to intersect potential façades but not so large as to capture features that are no longer perceptually part of the street section. Each sightline is intersected with the building footprints to identify the first building encountered, if any.

At the level of an individual Sight Point i on segment s and side $j \in \{L, R\}$, the result of this intersection can be summarised by three quantities: a binary variable indicating whether a building is present on that side; the distance $d_{s,j,i}$ from the Sight Point to the encountered façade along the perpendicular direction, if present; and the height $h_{s,j,i}$ of the encountered building, if height data are available. If no building is found within the search distance, the observations for that side may be recorded as missing or assigned special values.

3.4 Aggregation to street level

The Sight Point–level observations are then aggregated to street level for each side. For each street segment s and side $j \in \{L, R\}$, let N_s be the total number of Sight Points and $n_{s,j}$ the number of Sight Points where a building is present on side j . Let the set of setback distances where a building exists be $\{d_{s,j,i} : i = 1, \dots, n_{s,j}\}$, and the corresponding building heights be $\{h_{s,j,i} : i = 1, \dots, n_{s,j}\}$.

These quantities constitute the raw material for defining the three streetscape indicators. They describe, for each street segment and each

side, how often buildings are encountered, at what typical distances from the street, and with what characteristic heights.

To prepare for computing the HW Ratio, it is convenient to define an effective street half-width $w_{s,j,i}$ for each Sight Point where a building is present, which can be taken as the distance $d_{s,j,i}$ itself when considering the side independently. When both sides are built at a given sampling point, the full local width of the built corridor can be approximated as $d_{s,L,i} + d_{s,R,i}$. Street segments where there are no buildings on one or both sides, or where data are too sparse to compute meaningful statistics, are either treated separately for diagnostic purposes or assigned conservative indicator values reflecting their clearly unfavourable skeletal conditions.

4. The three indicators and their formulae

4.1 Continuity

Continuity is defined to quantify the proportion of the street length where a building is present along a given side. For street segment s and side $j \in \{L, R\}$, let N_s be the total number of Sight Points along the segment and $n_{s,j}$ the number of Sight Points where the perpendicular sightline intersects a building within the prescribed distance. Continuity is then given by:

$$\text{Continuity}_{s,j} = n_{s,j} / N_s$$

By construction, this ratio lies between 0 and 1. A value of 0 indicates that no building is encountered at any of the Sight Points on side j , while a value of 1 indicates that a building is present at every Sight Point on that side. Intermediate values reflect partial coverage. For example, $\text{Continuity}_{s,j} = 0.7$ indicates that roughly seventy per cent of the segment's length is directly lined by buildings on that side at the sampling resolution.

In some parts of the analysis, it is useful to work with the complement of Continuity, referred to as perforation. Perforation on side j of segment s is defined as:

$$\text{Perforation}_{s,j} = 1 - \text{Continuity}_{s,j} = 1 - (n_{s,j} / N_s)$$

The present protocol, however, consistently refers to the side-specific indicator as Continuity. To obtain a street-level Continuity value that combines both sides, a simple and intuitive approach is to average the two side-specific values:

$$\text{Continuity}_s = \frac{1}{2} (\text{Continuity}_{s,L} + \text{Continuity}_{s,R})$$

4.2 Alignment

Alignment captures the degree of regularity of façade positions along each side. It is derived from the distribution of setback distances $d_{s,j,i}$ measured at Sight Points where a building is present. For a given segment s and side j , the first step is to compute the median setback:

$$m_{s,j} = \text{median}\{d_{s,j,i} : i = 1, \dots, n_{s,j}\}$$

This median represents a typical façade line along the segment. The second step is to measure the dispersion of individual setback distances around

this reference line. A robust measure for this purpose is the median absolute deviation (MAD), defined as:

$$MAD_{s,j} = \text{median}\{ |d_{s,j,i} - m_{s,j}| : i = 1, \dots, n_{s,j} \}$$

To transform this misalignment into a normalised Alignment indicator bounded between 0 and 1, a linear rescaling with an upper cap is applied. Let $C > 0$ denote a reference value expressing the maximum setback variability compatible with a coherent façade line. Alignment is defined as:

$$\text{Alignment}_{s,j} = \max(0, \min(1, 1 - MAD_{s,j} / C))$$

In the present implementation, the reference value C is fixed at 50 metres, corresponding to a conservative upper bound on façade setback variability beyond which the built front is considered effectively incoherent at the scale of the street segment.

When $MAD_{s,j} = 0$, $\text{Alignment}_{s,j}$ equals 1, corresponding to perfect alignment. When $MAD_{s,j} = C$, Alignment becomes 0. Values between 0 and 1 represent intermediate levels of regularity.

At street level, Alignment may be aggregated symmetrically across both sides as:

$$\text{Alignment}_s = \frac{1}{2} (\text{Alignment}_{s,L} + \text{Alignment}_{s,R})$$

4.3 HW Ratio

The HW Ratio indicator approximates the degree of vertical enclosure of the street cross-section by relating building heights to the effective width of the space between façades. For each Sight Point i on street segment s and side j , a semi height-to-width ratio is defined as:

$$r_{s,j,i} = h_{s,j,i} / d_{s,j,i}$$

Here $h_{s,j,i}$ denotes the height of the encountered building and $d_{s,j,i}$ the setback distance from the street centreline. Street-level values are obtained by aggregating these local ratios, typically using the median:

$$\text{HW Ratio}_{s,j}^{\text{raw}} = \text{median}\{ r_{s,j,i} : i = 1, \dots, n_{s,j} \}$$

To avoid excessive influence of extreme local configurations, a cap R_{max} is applied. The final HW Ratio is therefore defined as:

$$\text{HW Ratio}_{s,j} = \min(\text{HW Ratio}_{s,j}^{\text{raw}}, R_{\text{max}})$$

Side-specific HW Ratios may be combined into a single street-level indicator by averaging:

$$\text{HW Ratio}_s = \frac{1}{2} (\text{HW Ratio}_{s,L} + \text{HW Ratio}_{s,R})$$

5. From indicators to composite interpretation: sigmoids and calibration

5.1 Indicator transformation via sigmoid functions

Although Continuity, Alignment and HW Ratio are already meaningful in their raw form, their relationship with main-street suitability is not necessarily linear. For example, increasing Continuity from 0.1 to 0.3 may have a much stronger effect than increasing it from 0.7 to 0.9. Similarly, Alignment may be largely acceptable up to a certain level of misalignment,

after which further irregularity quickly degrades the perceived quality of the street edge.

To account for such non-linearities, each indicator is transformed into a suitability score using a sigmoidal function. For a generic indicator value x , the suitability score is defined as:

$$S(x) = \alpha + L / (1 + \exp(-k (x - x_0)))$$

where α and L determine the range of the score, and k and x_0 determine the shape and position of the transition. Typically, α is chosen so that $S(x)$ takes values in a convenient interval, such as $[0, 1]$ or $[1, 100]$, and L is chosen accordingly.

In the implemented workflow, the sigmoid is used in its *normalised* form, with

$\alpha=0$ and $L = 1$. The resulting transformation is therefore:

$$p_X(x) = 1 / (1 + \exp(-k_X (x - x_{0_X})))$$

yielding a dimensionless *propensity (fit) score* bounded between 0 and 1.

For the three indicators, separate sigmoid functions are defined as follows:

$$S_{\text{cont}}(x) = \alpha_{\text{cont}} + L_{\text{cont}} / (1 + \exp(-k_{\text{cont}} (x - x_{0,\text{cont}})))$$

$$S_{\text{align}}(x) = \alpha_{\text{align}} + L_{\text{align}} / (1 + \exp(-k_{\text{align}} (x - x_{0,\text{align}})))$$

$$S_{\text{HW}}(x) = \alpha_{\text{HW}} + L_{\text{HW}} / (1 + \exp(-k_{\text{HW}} (x - x_{0,\text{HW}})))$$

The essential point is that the shape of each curve is tailored to how changes in the indicator relate to main-street suitability. For Continuity, values near zero may produce scores close to zero, with a rapid increase around a moderate threshold and then a plateau. For misalignment (via Alignment), the sigmoidal curve may be mirrored or defined over the inverted measure.

5.2 Composite enclosure score at side and street level

Once the three indicators have been transformed into suitability scores, they are combined. The protocol adopts a multiplicative approach at side

level, reflecting the idea that deficiencies in one dimension can limit the overall suitability even if the other dimensions are strong.

For a given street segment s and side j , the side-level composite score is defined as:

$$C_{s,j} = S_cont(Continuity_{s,j}) \times S_align(Alignment_{s,j}) \times S_HW(HW\ Ratio_{s,j})$$

This product is high only when all three component scores are reasonably high. If one component score is very low, the product is pulled down, reflecting the fact that a main-street-like environment requires a combination of structural properties.

To aggregate the two side-level composite scores into a single street-level value, a symmetric aggregation function is required. Rather than using a simple arithmetic mean, the protocol adopts a root mean square (RMS) aggregation of the left and right side scores:

$$C_s = \sqrt{(C_{s,L}^2 + C_{s,R}^2)}/\sqrt{2}$$

This choice reflects a modelling assumption. Compared to a simple mean, the RMS aggregation places greater emphasis on higher values and therefore assigns relatively higher scores to streets where one side exhibits strong morphometric conditions even if the facing side is weaker or partially unbuilt. Such asymmetric configurations are common in real urban environments—for instance along streets bordering parks, waterfronts, rail corridors, large institutional parcels or other open spaces—where a single continuous and well-defined built frontage can still play a structuring role for public space, pedestrian movement and activity concentration. At the same time, streets where both sides perform poorly remain strongly penalised. The RMS aggregation thus captures the frequent asymmetry of streetscapes while remaining symmetric with respect to left and right sides, and avoids unduly downgrading streets that possess a strong structural edge on only one side.

5.3 Calibration with points of interest

The parameters of the sigmoidal functions are calibrated using empirical data on activity, represented by points of interest (POIs) such as Foursquare venues.

Two continuous activity reference variables are used for calibration:

- (i) POI count within a 10 m buffer, and
- (ii) POI density defined as POI count divided by street length.

The sigmoid parameters are calibrated by maximising the Pearson correlation between the Composite Enclosure Fit Score and these reference variables.

Let θ denote the set of parameters defining the sigmoidal functions, including k_cont , $x_0,cont$, k_align , $x_0,align$, k_HW , x_0,HW , and any chosen α and L values.

For a given parameter set θ , the composite score $C_s(\theta)$ is computed for all streets. The association between morphology and activity is quantified using the Pearson correlation coefficient:

$$\rho(\theta) = \text{corr}(C_s(\theta), Y_s)$$

The calibration problem consists in selecting parameter values θ that maximise this correlation, which can be expressed as:

$$\theta^* = \arg \max_{\theta} \rho(\theta)$$

or equivalently as the minimisation of a loss function:

$$L(\theta) = -\rho(\theta)$$

Once calibration is complete, the resulting composite score $C_s(\theta^*)$ can be mapped and compared across the street network to identify streets where morphological conditions are favourable or unfavourable for main-street roles.

6. Results

The calibration procedure described above yields two closely related outcomes. On the one hand, it produces a set of sigmoidal curves for each of the three skeletal indicators – Continuity, Alignment and HW Ratio – which can be interpreted as propensity thresholds indicating how strongly different ranges of morphometric indicators are associated with higher levels of observed activity. On the other hand, it produces a combined propensity score for each street segment, obtained by combining the three indicator-specific sigmoids. This combined propensity is what we call the enclosed score, and it is the main morphological output to be used within EMC2 in conjunction with street centrality types, functional and transport data, and population.

6.1 Indicator-specific sigmoids as propensity functions

Once the sigmoidal functions calibrated, they can be read as propensity curves. To make this explicit, it is convenient to reformulate the sigmoids in a normalised logistic form. Although bounded between 0 and 1, these values do not represent probabilities in a statistical sense, but calibrated **propensity (fit) scores**, optimised to maximise correlation with observed POI-based activity measures. For each indicator X (which can be Continuity, Alignment or HW Ratio), and for each street segment s , we can write:

$$p_X(x) = 1 / (1 + \exp(-k_X(x - x_{0_X})))$$

In this formulation, $p_X(x)$ is a propensity score associated with indicator X , bounded between 0 and 1. It does not represent the propensity of a binary event, but rather a monotonic transformation of the indicator value that expresses how favourable a given morphological condition is with respect to observed activity intensity.

The parameters k_X and x_{0_X} control the steepness and the location of the transition, respectively. Low indicator values yield propensity scores close to 0, intermediate values correspond to a rapid increase in propensity, and high values lead to saturation effects where further improvements in the indicator produce only marginal gains.

The parameters of these sigmoidal functions are calibrated empirically by maximising the statistical association between the resulting composite propensity score and a continuous measure of street-level activity, rather than by fitting a binary classification model.

Each calibrated curve can therefore be read as follows. For Continuity, the sigmoid describes how the propensity that a street supports high Pol density increases as the proportion of built front along the segment rises. The lower part of the curve, where propensity remains near zero, corresponds to weak or fragmented built fronts that rarely host dense activity. The middle part around x_0 , Cont marks a transition zone: streets with Continuity in this range are sometimes, but not always, associated with high activity. Beyond this threshold, propensity rises rapidly and then saturates, indicating that once Continuity reaches sufficiently high levels, further increases do not fundamentally change the likelihood of activity.

For Alignment, a similar reading applies, but in this case the underlying raw quantity is misalignment, and the indicator is obtained after rescaling and inversion. The resulting sigmoid expresses how the propensity of high activity changes as the façade line becomes more coherent. Streets with very low Alignment scores (high misalignment) have a low propensity of belonging to the high-activity class. Around an intermediate zone, small improvements in alignment can substantially increase this propensity, while beyond a certain level of coherence the curve flattens and further refinement of the façade line has relatively little additional effect.

For the HW Ratio, the sigmoid describes the relationship between enclosure and activity. Very low HW Ratio values, typical of wide, lightly built corridors, correspond to low propensity of high Pol density. As HW Ratio increases towards an empirically determined threshold, the propensity rises, reflecting the idea that some degree of enclosure is conducive to concentrated activity and main-street-like environments. Beyond a certain range, the curve tends to plateau: highly enclosed streets are not necessarily more likely to be more active than streets with moderate enclosure, at least within the empirical context of the case studies.

In all three cases, the calibrated sigmoids thus act as propensity thresholds. They do not define hard cut-offs, but they indicate ranges of indicator values where the morphological conditions are typically associated with high or low activity. In graphical terms, each sigmoid can be plotted with the indicator on the horizontal axis and the propensity p_{high} on the vertical axis. The shape of these plots is one of the key results of the calibration step, as it provides an interpretable link between skeletal form and observed functional intensity.

6.2 Composite Enclosure Fit Score

While each indicator-specific sigmoid provides a separate propensity estimate, the protocol is primarily interested in a combined propensity that takes all three skeletal dimensions into account. The guiding idea is that a street segment is most likely to support main-street functions when Continuity, Alignment and HW Ratio are simultaneously in favourable ranges. Conversely, if one or more of these conditions are extremely poor, the likelihood of strong activity remains low even if the others are satisfactory.

For each street segment s , we therefore compute the three indicator-specific propensities:

$$p_{\text{Cont},s} = p_{\text{Cont}}(X_{\text{Cont},s})$$

$$p_{\text{Align},s} = p_{\text{Align}}(X_{\text{Align},s})$$

$$p_{\text{HW},s} = p_{\text{HW}}(X_{\text{HW},s})$$

where $X_{\text{Cont},s}$, $X_{\text{Align},s}$ and $X_{\text{HW},s}$ denote the values of the three indicators for street s . These quantities are indicator-specific propensity scores expressing how favourable each morphological dimension is with respect to observed activity intensity, considered independently.

To obtain a single combined propensity, the protocol adopts a multiplicative approach analogous to the composite score described earlier, but now explicitly in propensity terms. A simple formulation is:

$$P_s^{\text{enc}} = (p_{\text{Cont},s} \cdot p_{\text{Align},s} \cdot p_{\text{HW},s}) / Z$$

where Z is a normalising constant chosen so that P_s^{enc} lies in the interval $[0, 1]$. In practice, since each p_{\cdot} is itself in $[0, 1]$, the product is already bounded by 0 and 1. Normalisation may still be used for convenience or to emphasise particular ranges, but the key point is that the product emphasises streets where all three component propensities are high.

We refer to this combined propensity P_s^{enc} as the Composite Enclosure Fit Score (CEFS) for street s . The term reflects the fact that it summarises three aspects of enclosure-related skeletal form: the enclosure of the street edge by a continuous built front (Continuity), the enclosure of the public space by a coherent façade line (Alignment), and the volumetric enclosure of the cross-section (HW Ratio). It is important to stress that the enclosed score is not a deterministic classification but a propensity score: it expresses how likely a street, given its skeletal morphology, is to belong to the high-activity class as defined by the calibration data.

The enclosed score thus has a dual status. On the one hand, it is statistically grounded: its shape is informed by the empirical association between morphology and observed activities in given case studies. On the other hand, it remains a morphological indicator: it is still derived entirely from Continuity, Alignment and HW Ratio and does not directly encode activity data once the calibration is fixed.

6.3 Mapping and interpretation of the enclosed score

Once computed for all street segments in a metropolitan area, the enclosed score can be mapped and analysed spatially. Each segment s is assigned its enclosed score P_s^{enc} , which can be visualised using a colour ramp ranging, for example, from low-propensity segments (close to 0) to high-propensity segments (close to 1). This produces a metropolitan map of morphological main-street potential, interpreted in propensity terms.

Several patterns typically emerge. Segments in historic centres and traditional urban fabrics, where built fronts are continuous and aligned and where buildings of moderate height closely frame the streets, tend to receive high enclosed scores. Peripheral arterial roads with large setbacks, strip development and scattered buildings tend to score low. Mixed areas with some coherent frontages and some fragmented parts often show intermediate scores, reflecting their ambiguous or transitional position in the urban structure.

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Beyond visual inspection, the enclosed score can be analysed statistically. For instance, histograms or cumulative distributions can show how many streets fall into different propensity bands; cluster analyses can identify contiguous stretches of high-scoring segments; and cross-tabulations with other variables can reveal how enclosed score relates to street hierarchy, land use or socio-economic conditions.

It is important to reiterate that the enclosed score reflects morphological propensity, not functional reality. A street segment with a high enclosed score is structurally well-suited to host main-street functions, but it may currently be underused or under-programmed; conversely, a segment with a low enclosed score may still host some activities, especially if driven by external factors (for example, large attractors or transport hubs). Nevertheless, at the scale of a metropolitan area, the enclosed score provides a consistent and interpretable measure of built-form conditions that support or hinder the emergence of main streets.

7. Data Availability Caveat: Building Heights, Cross-City Comparability, and Future Prospects

A final methodological caveat concerns the availability and reliability of building height data across the five metropolitan case studies of the EMC2 project. As the analytical protocol developed in this deliverable includes the **HW Ratio** indicator as one of the three core morphometrics contributing to the computation of the streetscape enclosure score, the absence of consistent height information directly affects the comparability and completeness of the streetscape assessment.

For the French case studies—**Lille-Roubaix-Tourcoing** and the **French Riviera**—we benefit from detailed authoritative datasets that provide reliable building height estimates. These sources make it possible to compute the HW Ratio consistently along each street segment and to integrate this descriptor into the calibrated sigmoid functions used to derive the propensity enclosure score. As a result, the French metropolitan areas constitute the fully specified benchmark against which methodological refinements can be tested.

In contrast, for the other three metropolitan regions selected in the EMC2 project, the **height attribute is systematically missing** from OpenStreetMap (OSM) or is available only in a fragmentary, inconsistent form. Although OSM offers a robust representation of building footprints and street centreline geometries—allowing the computation of **Continuity** and **Alignment**—it does not currently provide the degree of completeness required for the HW Ratio to be used as a reliable third morphometric systematically across all cities. Consequently, the streetscape enclosure scores produced for **Vienna, Versilia, and Gothenburg** rely solely on the first two morphometrics (Continuity and Alignment), excluding the vertical dimension of enclosure from the composite propensity. This reduction does not invalidate the analytical framework: Continuity and Alignment alone capture a substantial portion of the skeletal streetscape geometry, and the two-indicator composite score still yields meaningful predictions

aligned with the EMC2 principles. Nevertheless, the absence of the HW Ratio limits the extent to which results across the five cities can be compared directly or aggregated into multi-site statistical analyses.

This asymmetry in data availability highlights a broader structural limitation of global open-data ecosystems. Even though building footprints are widely available through volunteered geographic information, **building heights remain unevenly documented**, partly due to data collection difficulties, partly due to the absence of open official records in many countries, which are used to feed OSM data. Until this gap is addressed, streetscape-scale morphological research will continue to face constraints when operating across multiple geographic contexts.

An important development, however, suggests a promising way forward. The recently released **Global Building Atlas** (GBA) by Zhu et al. (2025), available at <https://github.com/zhu-xlab/GlobalBuildingAtlas>, constitutes the first worldwide building dataset providing systematically estimated heights at the global scale using remote-sensing and deep learning methods. While the dataset remains under active evaluation and requires validation for application at the granularity needed for streetscape morphological analysis, it offers a near-term prospect for extending the full three-indicator methodology to all EMC2 case studies and beyond. Once its suitability is confirmed, the GBA could be used to recompute HW Ratios consistently across all metropolitan areas, thereby restoring the full analytical symmetry of the protocol and enabling uniform multi-site comparisons at the street-segment level.

In summary, the methodological framework presented in this deliverable is fully operational for all case studies, but the **completeness of the streetscape enclosure score currently varies** depending on the availability of height data. This limitation does not compromise the conceptual coherence of the EMC2 analytical protocol but does indicate a direction for future development as new global datasets mature.

8. Limitations and future developments

The analytical protocol presented here is intentionally focused on skeletal form as derived from street networks and building footprints. Several limitations and avenues for future enhancement can be identified.

A first limitation is the absence of explicit **entrance and window data**. While Continuity and Alignment describe the presence and coherence of façades, they do not reveal how many doors or windows open directly onto the street or how transparent ground floors are. Where address point datasets, building entrance inventories or façade surveys exist, these can be added as additional indicators, such as entrance density per unit length or inter-entrance distances, to bring the analysis closer to an explicit measure of constitutedness.

A second limitation is the approximation involved in estimating **street width** and thus the HW Ratio. Using distances from the centreline to façades provides a consistent and tractable method across large territories, but it does not distinguish between carriageway, sidewalks and

other components of the cross-section, nor does it account for irregularly shaped public spaces. Where more detailed data on curb lines, parcel boundaries or right-of-way exist, the HW Ratio could be refined by computing height-to-width ratios from these more precise geometries.

A third limitation is that the protocol is inherently **static** and morphology-based. Streets and main streets in particular are shaped by temporal dynamics: flows of people and vehicles at different times, evolving land-use patterns, shifting economic conditions and changing governance frameworks. The indicators developed here do not capture such temporal aspects directly, but they can be combined with time-stamped data on mobility, economic activity or land-use change in subsequent analyses.

Finally, the indicator ranges and the sigmoidal mappings are **context-sensitive**. While the overall forms of the functions are general, the precise thresholds where Continuity or HW Ratio becomes associated with higher activity may vary between cities with different urban histories, cultures or climates. This is partly why a calibration step is included. However, when the protocol is transferred beyond the EMC2 case studies, it will be important to revisit the calibration and to interpret the results in relation to local trajectories.

Despite these limitations, the protocol has several strengths. It is conceptually grounded in the EMC2 principles, operationalised with clear formulae, and based on data that are increasingly available across European cities. It offers a structured way to quantify skeletal conditions that underpin main-street potential, without prescribing a single ideal form. It also leaves room for gradual refinement as new data, methods and case studies become available.

9. Conclusion

This first part of Deliverable D2.2 has set out the theoretical and methodological foundations of an analytical protocol for assessing built-up form and public space along street networks within the EMC2 project. It has argued for the importance of focusing on skeletal streetscape morphology and has introduced three core indicators – **Continuity**, **Alignment** and **HW Ratio** – that capture essential properties of the street edge. These indicators have been precisely defined in terms of the underlying streetscape morphometrics produced by `momepy.streetscape`, with explicit formulae relating Sight Point-level measurements to street-level descriptors.

The document has explained how these indicators relate to EMC2 principles on main streets, how they can be transformed by sigmoidal functions into suitability scores, and how a multiplicative composite score can be constructed and calibrated against point-of-interest data to reflect empirically observed associations between morphology and activity. It has also discussed the limitations of a skeletal-only approach and highlighted possible extensions incorporating entrance data, parcel-based metrics and street “skin” descriptors.

Part 2 of D2.2 will build directly on this conceptual and formal foundation, translating the protocol into detailed pseudocode and implementation guidelines, and illustrating its application in EMC2 case studies. Together, the two parts will provide a comprehensive and reproducible toolkit for understanding how built form and public space, as organised along street networks, contribute to the emergence and consolidation of main streets in contemporary metropolitan regions.

10. References

- Alexander Ch., Ishikawa S., Silverstein M. (1977) *A Pattern Language: Towns, Buildings, Construction*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Appleyard, D. (1981). *Livable Streets*. University of California Press.
- Araldi A., Fleischmann M., Fusco G., Novotný M., 2025, Streetscape Morphometrics: Expanding Momepy to Analyze Urban Form from the Street Point of View, *SoftwareX*, ISSN 2352-7110, 31, 102242, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2025.102242>
- Fleischmann, M., Vybornova, A., Gaboardi, J.D., Brázdová, A., & Dančejová, D. (2026). Adaptive continuity-preserving simplification of street networks. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 123, 102354. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2025.102354>
- Fusco G., Berghauser Pont M., Cutini V., Psenner A., 2024, Guiding principles for the 15-minute city in peripheral areas: the emc2 model. In M. Cremaschi (dir.) *Game changer? Planning for just and sustainable urban regions*, Proceedings of AESOP Annual Congress, Paris, July 8th-12th 2024, Sciences Po – AESOP, ISBN 9789464981827, pp. 690-707, <https://hal.science/hal-04798781>
- Gehl, J. (2011) *Life Between Buildings: Using Public Space*. Washington, DC: Island Press.
- Harvey C., Aultman-Hall L. (2016) Measuring urban streetscapes for livability: A review of approaches. *The Professional Geographer* 68(1): 149–158.
- Zhu, X. X., Chen, S., Zhang, F., Shi, Y., & Wang, Y. (2025). GlobalBuildingAtlas: An open global and complete dataset of building polygons, heights and LoD1 3D models (arXiv:2506.04106). arXiv. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2506.04106>